
MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM IN THE HORMONAL MODULATION OF MENOPAUSE – PRESENTATION OF THE CHAKRAS/GLANDS PROTOCOL

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Menopause is the period in a woman's life between 40 and 60 years old, marked by the interruption of menstrual periods. Usually accompanied by psychosomatic symptoms, hot flashes, malaise, night sweats, nausea and lack of concentration. Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a natural, non-invasive, painless and low-cost therapeutic system that presents itself as an Integrative and Complementary Practice (PIC – Práticas Integrativas e Complementar in Portuguese) that acts in the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of bioelectric and biomagnetic dysfunctions of the body. The treatment aims at rebalancing human beings in all aspects of life, involving organic, energetic, emotional, psycho-emotional, spiritual dysfunctions and the Chakras. MB stimulates the body's homeostasis through Static Magnetic Fields, generated by therapeutic magnets and aims at neutralizing the organic environments affected by

bioelectromagnetic dysfunctions that may favor the development of pathologies. **Objective:** The objective of this study is to present a MB protocol for self-care, through the alignment and balance of the body's electromagnetic energy distribution centers, known as Chakras, for the treatment of menopausal symptoms. **Method:** The applied methodology was a descriptive and exploratory bibliographical review, structuring the Chakra/Gland protocol presented as a result of this research. **Conclusion:** The conclusion is that the presented protocol can stimulate the body's vital energy by acting directly on the endocrine interfaces, improving the physical, psycho-emotional and energetic system of women going through the menopause phase, minimizing the adverse effects of this period and, providing health and quality of life in a natural way.

Keywords: Menopause; Medicinal Biomagnetism; Chakras; Climacteric; Protocol; Quality of life; Integrative and Complementary Therapies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization defines menopause as a period in a woman's life when reproductive capacity ceases. The ovaries stop functioning and the production of steroids and hormone peptides decrease. Different physiological changes occur in the body, some resulting from ovarian function and menopausal phenomena and others due to the aging process. As Menopause approaches, many women experience symptoms, which are usually transient and not harmful, but unpleasant and sometimes disabling.

The concept of Menopause arose from an article by the French gynecologist Charles Pierre de Gardanne, published in 1816, called "Advice to women entering the critical age". In it, the researcher describes the syndrome called "La ménopausie" (Latin term derived from the Greek, "men" lunar count related to the period of a month and "paüsis", pause), referring to the interruption of the menstrual cycle (TRENCH and SANTOS , 2005).

According to the Ministry of Health in Brazil (2008), Climacteric and Menopause "are not diseases", but a natural phase in a woman's life that many go through without complaints or medication.

“In women’s lives, unlike what happens to men, there are concrete and objective milestones that signal different phases or passages in their lives (Figure 1), such as menarche, hymen rupture, last menstruation. They are visible landmarks on the physical body and each culture invests them with its rubric. In our culture, historically, numerous conditions (physical and psychological) have been associated with menopause” (TRENCH and SANTOS, 2005).

Figure 1: Stages in a woman’s life

Source: Adapted from ROCHA (2010).

According to Silva (2006), Menopause disorders do not appear in a standardized way in all women and he states that the arrival of this phase, or the passage through the period from 40 years to 60 years, is impregnated with significant biopsychosocial and cultural aspects that influence directly on the symptomatology. There are many transformations and transitions that women undergo during this period.

Menopause is marked by changes in the structure and function of the ovaries. The ovarian follicles decrease and mark the beginning of this phase with a sudden drop in estrogen, progesterone and an increase in the hormones FSH and LH. This process occurs due to the stimulation of the hypophysis by the decrease in the production of inhibin and estradiol. The alterations cause the disappearance of the menstrual and reproductive period, generate hot flashes and night sweats, psychosomatic symptoms, nausea and lack of concentration (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2016), physical and psychological changes accompanied by discomfort, insomnia, vaginal dryness, palpitations, joint pain, dizziness, headaches, irritability, memory failures or forgetfulness, anxiety and depression (ROCHA and ROCHA, 2010).

Talaulikar (2020), comments that 85% of women complain of physical and psycho-emotional manifestations related to menopause. Long-term estrogen deficiency can have repercussions on the bone, cardiovascular and urinary systems (ROCHA and ROCHA, 2010). Symptoms are associated with changes in neuronal modulation mediated by adrenaline, noradrenaline, serotonin, opioids and gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA) on pituitary hormones, as well as changes in their levels due to estrogen deficiency (PASSOS *et al.*, 2017).

Western medicine attributes menopause symptoms to estrogen hormone deficiency and indicates hormone replacement to alleviate them (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2016), while for Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), symptoms are the result of Yin and Yang imbalance, hot waves happen due to the deficiency of Yin in the kidney, other symptoms may be related to deficiencies in the energy centers, the Chakras and the treatment of these deficient energies can lead to an improvement in the general condition, without the need for hormone therapy (HUANG, 2020).

Gerber (1988), reports that in human anatomy there are Chakras and that these are closely related to the glands and their functions. The Chakras promote the capture of superior energies, transforming and distributing them to the physical body, translating them into hormonal and physiological chemical reactions essential for the survival of the organism.

Huang (2020), suggests the alignment of the Chakras, physical exercises and changes in eating habits to alleviate menopausal imbalances. Otani and Barros (2011) report that the demand for treatments with PICs has increased and people are looking for gentler methods, with fewer side effects and that considers the human being as a whole, body, soul and spirit. According to Contactore and collaborators (2015), integrative medicine is the combination of conventional and non-conventional medicine that together can offer more benefits to patients.

1.1 Endocrine System

The endocrine system is formed by hormone-producing glands that are released into the bloodstream and are responsible for various organic functions. As illustrated in Figure 2, this system is composed of the hypothalamus, pineal and hypophysis (cephalic level), thyroid, parathyroid, thymus, adrenals, pancreas and gonads (ovaries and testicles). The pancreas and the gonads have an endocrine and exocrine function (producing pancreatic juice and gametes, respectively), so they are considered mixed glands (LEITE *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 2: Major Endocrine Glands

Source: Adapted from Romero (2015).

The pineal endocrine gland produces melatonin, a sleep-regulating hormone, secreted exclusively at night (dark). Its function is to provide pace for the organism to carry out its functions throughout the day, such as signaling whether it is day or night, bringing perceptions of the seasons by regulating the circadian cycle. It confers rhythm to several neuroendocrine functions, modulating reproductive activity and metabolic activity (SERAPHIM *et al.*, 2000).

Gümbel (2016) points out that the reproductive glands are mixed glands, their external secretion produces gametes, whereas the endocrine secretion produces estrogen and progesterone in women and in men, testosterone. Hormones are

regenerative centers, responsible for cell reproduction, they determine healthy metabolism and the aging process in the human body.

The pituitary is the essential hormonal regulatory and directing center, controls the metabolic balance, regulates and stimulates the subordinate hormonal glands (thyroid, thymus, pancreas, adrenals, gonads) to increase or cease the distribution of their hormones. It was considered by philosophers as the center of human consciousness, the organ of sense of self-consciousness, it is the point where man “grabs” to himself and discovers his “I” (GÜMBEL, 2016).

The thyroid gland regulates combustion metabolism by increasing oxygen absorption by cells through thyroxine (T3 and T4). The thymus has an effect on immune functions by acting as an enhancer in the lymphatic organs (spleen, palatine tonsils, lymph nodes). The pancreas synthesizes two hormones with antagonistic and complementary effects, insulin and glucagon. The adrenal or suprarenal glands play a regulatory role in the sympathetic autonomic nervous system and are metabolism control centers through the secretion of adrenaline, which helps to control blood pressure, heart rate and sweat production (GÜMBEL, 2016).

1.2 Chakras

Chakras have been cited since 2000 BC. by Vedic literature, as “wheel of light” or “center of energy”. They are also called Padma and are represented as Lotus Flowers. Mentioned countless times throughout history and thanks to the tantric culture, the Chakras have become an integral and real yoga system philosophy, transmitted from master to disciple (MICHELIS, 2005; CRUZAR, 2006).

Tantrism established itself as a philosophy based on a set of scriptures by unknown Indian authors, dating from the 7th century and addressing culture, sexuality, health, food, spirituality and concepts of ethics and morals. The objective of tantric philosophy is the integral development of the human being in the physical, mental and spiritual aspects. The balance of the Chakras plays an integral and fundamental part of this process (TIMALSINA, 2011).

Chakras are located in various regions of the body such as hands and feet or any other member, they provide passage for energy to enter and exit and help to regulate all types of energy flow, such as physical, mental, emotional or spiritual. The seven main chakras are aligned vertically from the base of the torso to the top of the head. Each of them is related to the maintenance of specific physical, mental and emotional functions and are connected to an endocrine gland or nervous plexus, as shown in Figure 3 (RAMKUMAR and PRIYAL, 2016; CHASE, 2018; SPEZZIA and SPEZZIA, 2018).

Figure 3: Relation between main Chakras and Endocrine Glands

Caption: The image shows the location of the Chakras, their colors, energy vortices coming out of the front and back of the body and their correspondence with the glands.

Source: Adapted from Cross (2010).

The Chakras project energy towards the spine, the anterior part of the body and the crown. The projection of energy measures approximately 10 centimeters outside the body, as shown in Figure 2. The Chakras rotate and radiate light, colors, frequencies and specific vibrations from each of them (RAMKUMAR and PRIYAL, 2016; CHASE, 2018; SPEZZIA and SPEZZIA, 2018).

Based on an overview of the work of John R. Cross (2010), Chase (2018), carried out an extensive study on acupuncture and the Chakras energy system, publishing a study on the correspondence of the Chakras in imbalance with the neuroendocrine system, emotions and the diseases, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The 7 Main Chakras **Table 1:** The 7 Main Chakras

MAIN CHAKRAS– Location – endocrine connections	Correspond ence of the Chakras with ganglia and organs	Emotions related to energy imbalance of the Chakras	Diseases caused by imbalances of the Chakras
1st CHAKRAROOT or BASE – Base of spine, perineum to the supra pubic – Adrenal (suprarenal)	Pelvic nerve plexus Spin e, kidneys, bladder, large intestine.	Insecurity, doubt, fear of change, scarcity, anxiety, loneliness, no foundation for family and orphans.	Allergy, eczema, addictions, immune system problems, nephritis, cystitis, lower back problems, lethargy, fatigue, depression, stiff joints, osteoarthritis and intestinal disorders.

<p>2nd CHAKRA SACRAL orUTERINE/ PROSTATIC – Between the pelvis and the belly button – Ovaries/Testicles</p>	<p>Inferiormes enteric gan glion. Ilium, repro dutor organ.</p>	<p>Envy, lust, jealousy, promiscuity and lack of desire.Excessive limits, poor communication and sensitiveness in excess.</p>	<p>Prostatitis, testicular and uterine diseases, impotence,ovarian and bladder problems, bed wetting, uterine fibroids,lower back pain, arthritis and all menstrual problems.</p>
<p>3rd CHAKRAUMBILI CAL orSOLAR PLEXUS – Mid abdômen- Pancreas</p>	<p>Ganglion of the celiac plexus. Liver , gallbladder, stomach, spleen, duodenum, pancreas.</p>	<p>Depression claustrophobia, lowenergy and self-esteem, rigid beliefs,stubbornn ess, resistance to change, arrogance and power- hungriness.</p>	<p>Pancreatitis, stomach ulcers, hepatitis, liver cancer, gallbladder disorders, diabetes, digestive disorders, liver problems, chronic fatigue, lower thoracic spine pain, gastrointestinal organs.</p>
<p>4th CHAKRAHEART – Center of chest, middle of sternum- Thymus</p>	<p>Celiac Plexus. Heart, circulation, vagus nerve.</p>	<p>Crying, anxiety and self-pity, depression and remarkableinabilit y to give or receive love.</p>	<p>Cardiac and circulatory disorders, nervous breakdowns, hypertension, angina, sleep disturbances, tremors, breast cancer, shortness of breath, tachycardia and scoliosis.</p>
<p>5th CHAKRA THROAT – Bottom of the</p>	<p>Cervical ganglion Bottom Lun gs, bronchi,</p>	<p>Paranoid and shy, very introverted, insecureand agoraphobic. Lack</p>	<p>Asthma, bronchitis, sore throats, colitis, irritable bowelsyndrome,</p>

throat – Thyroid and parathyroid	larynx, pharynx, vagus nerve, large intestine.	of expression, repressed emotions and inability to change direction in life.	diarrhea, laryngitis, thyroid and parathyroid disease, temporomandibular joint disorder, hoarseness and loss of taste.
6th CHAKRA FRONT / THIRD EYE – Above the eyebrows, center of the forehead – Pituitary and pineal thalamus and hypothalamus	Superior cervical ganglion. Left and lower brain. Ears, nose, left eye.	Anger, stress, indecision, irrationality, indifference, anxiety, unstable or easily changing mind/opinions, lacking moral courage and discontent.	Cataracts, headaches, migraines, left eye problems, brain diseases, deafness, dizziness, dyslexia, cervical spine arthritis and infectious diseases.
7th CHAKRA CROWN – Top of the head.- Pineal gland	Pineal gland Right brain, superior brain, right eye.	Melancholy, delusions and phobias/delusions. arrogance, pride, hallucinations, apathy and not donating.	Epilepsy, headaches, insomnia, migraines, multiple sclerosis, right eye problems, dementia, melancholy and depression.

Source: Adapted from Bossa (2021a) and Chase (2018).

The Chakras as centers of reception, transformation and distribution of the body's electromagnetic energy penetrates the 7 energy layers of the human biofield, each of which is an electromagnetic layer that surrounds the physical form and the lines of force that surround a magnet. The Chakras are related to magnetism, electromagnetism and the main endocrine glands and can be harmonized with the electromotive force of magnetic fields (CHASE, 2018).

1.3 Medicinal Biomagnetism

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is an alternative and complementary treatment system that can promote the person's physical, mental and spiritual health through bioenergetic, biomagnetic and bioelectric principles, using static magnetic fields, generated by medium intensity magnets that depolarize biomagnetic fields disorders present at specific points in the body (GOIZ, CASTELÁN and CASTELÁN, 2005).

Through the magnetic energy generated by the magnets, which vary in intensity between 1000 and 7500 Gauss (0.1 to 0.75 Tesla), MB prevents, balances and neutralizes energy distortions, treating numerous health disorders. It fulfills the functions of energy diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

The therapy has been practiced for more than 30 years and over this time several protocols have been developed, which are applied by Biomagnetism therapists who apply the technique, for the treatment and prevention of various dysfunctions of the immune, glandular, nervous, gastrointestinal, excretory, reproductive system, among others (MARTÍNEZ, 2019; BOSSA, 2021b, 2021c).

The technique is considered integrative medicine, as it addresses the individual as a whole and is based on conventional medical principles of anatomy, biology, biochemistry, biophysics, physiology, pathophysiology and microbiology, based on magnetism, entropy, symbiosis, potential hydrogen (pH), magnetic resonance imaging, fluid rheology and homeostasis. It acts at a physical level by identifying and correcting bioelectrical dysfunctions and at a bioenergetic level on emotional, psycho-emotional, sophrological, malignant, spiritual, deficiency, intoxication, Chakras and chromosomes problems (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008 and 2014).

According to Goiz Durán (2008), energy imbalance triggers pathological and pathogenic manifestations in the body are originated by two poles, a South pole that attracts the positive charges of biochemical elements, such as H⁺, and a North pole that attracts the negative charges, such as OH⁻. When the elements

that make up this biochemical imbalance are found in magnetic resonance, they form a Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) and are treated with MB magnets.

According to Goiz Durán together with collaborators (2005) and Martínez (2017), there are BMPs that are related to the energetic imbalance of the glands and that can act on the Chakras: BMP1 Pituitary/Ovary (Ovary Dysfunction); BMP2 Thymus/Adrenal; BMP3 Thymus/Thymus (Thymus Dysfunction); BMP4 Pineal/Pineal (Pineal Gland Dysfunction); BMP5 Thyroid/Thyroid (Thyroid gland dysfunction, hyper- or hypothyroidism); BMP6 Adrenal/Adrenal (Adrenal Dysfunction); BMP7 Ovary/Ovary (Ovary Dysfunction); BMP8 Testicle/Testicle (Hormonal and testicular dysfunction); BMP9 Parathyroid/Parathyroid (Parathyroid Dysfunction); BMP10 Pituitary/Pituitary gland (pituitary dysfunction).

The endocrine glands are responsible for distributing the energy received by the main nervous centers, and through them it is possible to promote the body's natural health and a person's energy state, recomposing their vital energy (GOIZ, CASTELÁN and CASTELÁN, 2005). According to Bossa (2021a, 2021c) the application of the Double Magnet, shown in Figure 3, can provide electromagnetic energy to the glands to modulate their functioning and balance the Chakras.

Figure 4: Double magnet

Caption: Illustrative image of the Double Magnets. **Source:** Bossa (2021a)

A Double Magnet has a polypropylene base where two neodymium magnets, grid 35, with opposite polarities are attached, with an average magnitude of 3,200 Gauss, separated by a thin layer and encapsulated according to the MB convention, as shown in Figure 4 (BOSSA, 2021a, 2021c).

Esprega (2017) mentions that living beings are composed of and influenced by energy and that in every organism there are energy points that, when they rotate harmonically, keep the organs and muscles in perfect working order, even influencing emotional and rational life. These energy points, called Chakras, can become unbalanced through internal or external stimuli (ESPREGA, 2017). The Chakras in their anterior exit vortices coincide with the MB points of application of the magnets on the main glands, both of which benefit from the treatment with the Double Magnets (BOSSA, 2021a).

This study aims to present a MB protocol for self-care, through the alignment and balance of the Chakras with Double Magnet, aiming at the recovery of glandular functions for the treatment of signs and symptoms that are related to menopause.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research used a bibliographical review with a theoretical construction that approaches the qualitative and exploratory approach, considering the interpretation and analysis of the elements obtained through the bibliographical survey, carrying out a theoretical-reflexive study of the criteria of the selected works on the information obtained from the specific themes (GIL, 1991).

The databases Scielo, Pubmed, Medline and Google Scholar were accessed to find articles using the descriptors: Menopause, Climacteric, Hormones, Glands, Chakras, Quality of Life and Integrative and Complementary Therapies, as well as the combination of descriptors Chakra and Menopause, published in period from 2000 to 2022.

The inclusion criteria for this study were works in English, Portuguese and Spanish, giving priority to articles with DOI – Digital Object Identifier (Digital Object Identifier), and available in full on the platforms. Incomplete articles, publications prior to the year 2000, in languages other than those described above, paid articles and articles that did not cover the theme of this study were excluded from the searches.

The research also used books and due to the scarcity of works on Medicinal Biomagnetism, the search for the basis and presentation of the MB protocol for menopausal disorders was carried out in the virtual library of the graduate program of Instituto Par Magnético Institute – IPM.

The bibliographic survey for this study started in August 2021 and ended in November 2022.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To fulfill the objective of this study, 31 studies were selected. From the researched bases, 12 articles were selected, as shown in Table 2, two of them without DOI, but of great relevance for the research.

After finding the 31 works related to the theme of Menopause, Chakras and MB and their protocols, the exclusion criteria were applied and the material used was: 8 works on MB from the virtual library of PAR Magnético Institute – IPM (3 of which are protocols), 8 on the Chakras, 1 on human physiology, 1 on sexuality, 1 on fundamentals of holistic theory, 1 Gynecology manual and 1 work to support the type of methodological study.

Table 2 : Result of the methodological application of articles considered in the study

Source: The authors

The bibliographical survey indicated that most women in the world experience menopausal disorders, complain of physical manifestations such as the sensation of hot flashes and perspiration, psychological and emotional changes that can be influenced by beliefs and values prevalent in the sociocultural environment. Regardless of the circumstances involved, women experiencing menopausal disorders need to have their corresponding care and support needs identified, understood and addressed based on their personal and contextual perspectives. With as women's life expectancy increases, they will spend a significant number of years of their lives in this phase (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2016).

As a result of the analysis of studies related to menopause, Medicinal Biomagnetism and the Chakras, the MB protocol that complies with the purpose of this study was identified, the Chakras/Glands Protocol was created and developed as a therapeutic system by Bossa (2021a and 2021c) . The Chakras/Glands Protocol, shown in Figure 5, was selected for presentation in this study because it has the purpose of acting directly on the main Chakras and endocrine glands.

Figure 5: Chakras/Glands Protocol

Chakras

Medicinal Biomagnetism

USING ONLY 1 DOUBLE MAGNET

The double magnet can be applied in an organized daily circuit starting with the first chakra, the root/base chakra, and working your way up, one magnet each day, until the Crown chakra is reached

USING 3 DOUBLE MAGNETS

Start with the Inferior Chakra Triangle (1st, 2nd and 3rd Chakras)

On the second day, special attention to the Heart Chakra

On the third day, the Superior Chakra Triangle (5th, 6th and 7th Chakras)

USING 4 DOUBLE MAGNETS

With more magnets, it is possible to start with Inferior Chakra Triangle (1st, 2nd and 3rd Chakras) and Heart Chakra. On the following day, repeat the Heart Chakra and add the Superior Chakra Triangle (5th, 6th and 7th Chakras)

USING 7 DOUBLE MAGNETS

Apply the magnets on all Chakras to harmonize the totality of the glands bioelectric system and the organism as a whole

OBS: Apply the magnets during 30 minutes daily.

Repeat 3 to 7 cycles, as necessary.

Good relaxing music or binaural frequencies can enhance the treatment's effect

Source: Adapted from Bossa (2021a).

According to Huang (2020) both menopause and the Chakras are related to the endocrinological system. The suggested protocol can alleviate and even end menopause disorders and troubles by nourishing the energy centers with the electromagnetism generated by the static magnetic fields of the Double Magnets applied in the region corresponding to the Chakras (BOSSA, 2021a).

The Chakras/Glands Protocol should be applied according to the number of magnets, time available and can be repeated according to the woman's needs, from 3 to 7 cycles, with a minimum time of 30 minutes daily, and may have an interval of up to 7 days to start a new cycle (BOSSA, 2021a).

Studies suggest that Chakras are formed by electromagnetic layers that surround the body (RAMKUMAR, 2016; CHASE, 2018; SPEZZIA and SPEZZIA, 2018), in the same way that the lines of force that surround magnets. The MB can adjust the energy imbalances that trigger pathological and pathogenic manifestations in the body, it can balance the BMPs related to the dysfunctions

of the endocrine glands linked to the 7 main Chakras (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008, BOSSA, 2021a, 2021c).

Bossa (2021a and 2021c), developed the Chakras/Glands Protocol based on the therapeutic system of Medicinal Biomagnetism, with the aim of balancing the energy centers through the electromagnetism generated by the static magnetic fields of the Double Magnets applied on the region corresponding to the Chakras. The Double Magnets act on the main Chakras and endocrine glands, encouraging physical, emotional and spiritual health and well-being.

The application of the protocol is simple and can be used by health professionals, therapists or even at home by the person. The technique consists of placing the Double Magnet on each Chakra according to the intensity of symptoms, availability of magnets and time (Figure 5). The treatment suggestion to stimulate hormonal modulation is to apply the Double Magnet in contact with the body, with the north or negative pole on the right hemibody and the south or positive pole on the left hemibody, on the frontal vortices of Chakras 1 to 6 and on the crown of the head on Chakra 7 (BOSSA, 2021a, 2021c).

To Rocha and Rocha (2010) the decrease of ovarian hormones can lead to glandular dysfunctions that trigger various physical, emotional and psychosocial disorders. According to Bossa (2021a), the objective of applying the Chakras/Glands Protocol, as shown in Figure 6, is related to the energy balance that leads to the modulation of glandular functions, serving as a painless and low-cost treatment for several health disorders, among them the ones caused during menopausal phase. The alignment and balance of energy centers can promote proper glandular functioning, adjusting the body as a whole, bringing general well-being and increasing the person's quality of life (TIMALSINA, 2011; CROSS, 2010; ESPREGA, 2017; CHASE , 2018).

Figure 6: Objective of the Chakras/Glands Protocol

Source: The authors

It is possible to regain the natural state of physical, emotional and psychosocial health, restoring the vital energy of the Chakras through electromagnetic stimuli since they are energy fields that, as described in Table 1, can present energy imbalances related to emotions and physiological disorders (CHASE, 2018).

With the activation and awakening of the Chakras through the right means, a person can evolve and enjoy the higher spheres of being. The seven Chakras are the centers of the energy system in the astral body, and the nadis are the channels that distribute this energy. When they are awakened and activated, a human being not only becomes aware of the higher spheres of existence, but also acquires the power to enter these spheres, strengthening him/herself and giving life to dimensions (HIROSHI and MOTOYAMA, 1981).

4. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

This study proposal brings an alternative protocol, the Chakras/Glands Protocol, which is painless, low cost and complementary to allopathic treatment, for hormonal modulation and menopausal disorders. This protocol has the potential to offer better physical and emotional conditions to women who are living this phase, even favoring those who have some type of allergy or side effects to medications.

This study sought to demonstrate the potential that the alternative and complementary treatment of Medicinal Biomagnetism can bring to society, directly impacting people's quality of life, and corroborate so that the theme can

become a possible object of scientific studies, in view of theoretical evidence regarding the benefits of MB in harmonizing and helping to treat symptoms, improving the energetic, psycho-emotional, physical and spiritual system, promoting general wellbeing in a natural way.

Given the lack of research on the subject, more studies are needed to show the results obtained with the application of the MB Chakras/Glands protocol as an auxiliary resource in the hormonal modulation of menopause.

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